

PEELNAPPLE COOKIE PRODUCTION

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Peelnapple Cookie Production

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Abstract

This study aimed to evaluate the physicochemical properties, acceptability, and marketability of "PEELNAPPLE" cookies, produced using 125 grams, 250 grams, and 375 grams of pineapple peel, banana peel, and pulp. Evaluations were conducted by students, Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers, and bakers in Antipolo City during the 2023-2024 school year. The study specifically addressed the production process, physicochemical analysis, acceptability levels, marketability, and respondent feedback. "PEELNAPPLE" cookies were produced through a method involving the drying, powdering, and blending of pineapple and banana peels and pulp with standard cookie ingredients. Physicochemical analysis indicated a pH of 5.40, a moisture content of 6.91%, potassium levels of 655 mg, and a negative result for Salmonella, demonstrating safety and consumer suitability. Acceptability was assessed using the Nine-point Hedonic Scale across appearance, aroma, taste, and texture. Findings indicated varying levels of acceptability: cookies with 125 grams were rated as "Very Much Acceptable," while those with 250 grams were rated as "Moderately Acceptable," and those with 375 grams ranged from "Moderately Acceptable" to "Slightly Acceptable." Significant differences were found in aroma, taste, appearance, and texture based on the amount of peels used. Marketability, assessed using the Five-point Likert Scale, was determined to be high for all proportions, with no significant differences across groups concerning production cost, supply availability, and consumer demand. Respondent suggestions included enhancing taste and aroma by adding vanilla, sugar, and chocolate chips, and promoting the cookies in local markets. Overall, "PEELNAPPLE" cookies were found to be a nutritious, appealing, and marketable product, well-received as a sustainable alternative for a broad consumer base.

Keywords: *peelnapple, cookie, acceptability, marketability, philippines*

Introduction

The food processing industry, which includes the processing of fruits and vegetables, is the second largest contributor of waste to the environment, following domestic sewage. The fruit and vegetable processing industries generate a significant quantity of waste that contains many valuable components with great nutritional value and considerable commercial potential (Alkozai, 2020). Many technological methodologies are employed in the food sector in conjunction with product development trends to create innovative and nutritious products. As stated, product development is being integrated to reduce waste by developing new products while yielding profitable advantages for the food sector. Therefore, product development has been employed to promote the recycling of products, particularly in regions where edible waste can also be utilized effectively.

The utilization of fruit by-products has recently gained popularity as a trend, and numerous research are currently being conducted to assess their impact on culinary attributes. The market's primary driver is consumers' growing emphasis on health and wellness. There has been an increasing focus on functional food items and the health and well-being of consumers. As a result, there has been a heightened interest in including vitamins, minerals, unsaturated fatty acids, bioactive chemicals, and fiber in food products. Utilizing fruit and vegetable by-products in diverse methods might be exceedingly advantageous for the promotion of sustainable food growth for several reasons:

Minimizing Food Waste: By using by-products, we decrease the quantity of food waste produced throughout the food manufacturing process. Approximately one-third of the total global food production is wasted, as reported by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO). By repurposing by-products, we may effectively reduce or alleviate the amount of trash generated.

Resource efficiency is achieved by utilizing by-products, which allows for a more optimal utilization of the resources allocated to food production, including water, land, and energy. This enhanced efficiency plays a role in promoting overall sustainability by diminishing the environmental impact of food production.

Economic advantages: Using by-products can generate supplementary sources of income for farmers and food producers. Instead of discarding these by-products as trash, they can be converted into goods that have added value, which helps to enhance profitability and economic resilience in the food business.

Nutritional value: Fruits and vegetables produce byproducts rich in dietary fiber, vitamins B1 and B2, and antioxidants. Adding these secondary products to food increases their nutritional value. Fruits and vegetables produce byproducts rich in dietary fiber, vitamins B1 and B2, and antioxidants.

Innovation and product diversification can be achieved by exploring novel applications for by-products, which can drive advancements in the development of food items. Diversification can generate fresh market prospects and satisfy the increasing need for sustainable

and nourishing food choices.

Environmental Benefits: Utilizing fruit and vegetable by-products aids in lessening the adverse environmental effects linked to food production, such as the emission of greenhouse gases, water consumption, and soil deterioration, by diminishing food waste and optimizing resource use.

In this regard, sustainable food development strategies utilizing by-products can provide favorable social outcomes such as bolstering local farmers, enhancing food security, and nurturing community resilience.

In addition, incorporating by-products into food production is a mutually beneficial approach that positively impacts the environment, economy, and society, promoting a more sustainable and resilient food system.

Accordingly, In the name of food sustainability and creativity, cookies serve as one of the most common snacks on tables and can be done in various ways. Cookies are extensively consumed globally as easily accessible and convenient food items, providing a higher nutritional value compared to other individual food sources (Alam, 2020). The Philippines, for one, has seen the development of numerous cookie varieties made from various ingredients, including vegetables, root crops, fruits, and more. These cookies are widely enjoyed as a snack and for other gatherings (Las Pinas et al., 2022). Using vegetable peel in pastry production, such as cookies, is beneficial in addressing consumer expectations.

This study sought to produce cookies using pineapple, banana pulp, and banana peel.

The paper highlighted the increasing demand for plant-based alternatives and emphasized their potential to influence the food sector's future as consumer preferences change. Currently, individuals are actively pursuing healthier options for their nutritional choices. In a country that is grappling with a persistent issue of hunger, this fortified product has the potential to provide a viable solution (Sharma, 2023). Furthermore, it signified an innovative deviation from conventional commercial cookies that usually emphasize only one ingredient.

The developed pastry product is expected to be marketed as "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies." Thus, the researcher decided to enhance the health benefits of the main elements utilized. This study specifically examined the effect of appearance, smell, texture, and taste on the overall acceptability of the "PEELNAPPLE" cookies.

The success of this research was mainly beneficial for the researcher's school community, as they encouraged pupils and teachers to adopt healthy snack options. Small business owners may also generate revenue through the commercialization of "PEELNAPPLE" cookies. In addition, these initiatives would promote cooperation between the industry and food technology expected to share their knowledge and skills as regards innovation in foodstuffs.

The opportunities created by this collaboration significantly benefit the academic community and agriculture.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the physicochemical analysis, level of acceptability, and marketability of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies with 125 grams, 250 grams, and 375 grams of pineapple peel, banana peel, and pulp as evaluated by the students, TLE teachers, and bakers during the school year 2023-2024 in Antipolo City. Specifically, it sought answers to the following question.

1. How can the "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies be produced out of pineapple peel, banana peel, and pulp with 125 grams, 250 grams and 375 grams?
2. What is the physicochemical analysis of "PEELNAPPLE" cookies with 125 grams, 250 grams, and 375 grams of pineapple peel, banana peel, and pulp in terms of the following
 - 2.1 pH level;
 - 2.2 Moisture content;
 - 2.3 Potassium; and
 - 2.4 Salmonella?
3. What is the level of acceptability of the "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies as evaluated by students, TLE teachers, and bakers with 125 grams, 250 grams, and 375 grams of pineapple peel, banana peel, and pulp on the following criteria:
 - 3.1 Appearance;
 - 3.2 Aroma;
 - 3.3 Taste; and
 - 3.4 Texture?
4. Are there significant differences among the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability of "PEELNAPPLE" cookies with 125 grams, 250 grams, and 375 grams of pineapple peel, banana peel, and pulp in terms of the abovementioned criteria?
5. What is the level of marketability of prepared "PEELNAPPLE" cookies with 125 grams, 250 grams, and 375 grams of pineapple peel, banana peel, and pulp in terms of the given criteria as perceived by the three groups of respondents?
 - 5.1 Production cost;

5.2 Supply availability; and

5.3 Consumer demand?

6. Are there significant differences among the perceptions of the three groups of respondents on the marketability of prepared “PEELNAPPLE” cookies with 125 grams, 250 grams, and 375 grams of pineapple peel, banana peel, and pulp in terms of the abovementioned criteria?

7. What are the comments and suggestions that can be offered by the respondents with 125 grams, 250 grams, and 375 grams of pineapple peel, banana peel, and pulp to improve the product?

Methodology

This section discusses the method of research used, the sources of data, the data gathering instrument, the data gathering procedure, and the statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

The study used a quantitative research design. According to Bhandari (2023), the objective of quantitative research is to determine the number of persons who have specific beliefs, behaviors, or emotions. Quantitative research involves gathering and examining numerical data. It was utilized for identifying patterns and averages, making forecasts, testing causality, and extrapolating the findings to a broader population.

Descriptive correlation is a survey method that gathers information without altering the survey subject. According to Bhat (2023), there are various sorts of descriptive correlation methodologies, each examined in a somewhat distinct manner. Descriptive correlation studies focused on reporting connections between variables without seeking to establish a causal relationship.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the students, TLE teachers, and bakers from the Antipolo City division. Purposive sampling was employed to guarantee a better questionnaire response rate and a representative sample. The purposive sample included a school with which the researcher has a personal connection and is ready to assist in completing the questionnaire of this study. Moreover, the researcher sought assistance from the school's critical administrators to gain support from the students and teachers to fill in the questionnaires for this study. This study did not limit the selection of research respondents, as any students and teachers connected with the subject schools could be potential respondents in the survey. However, the sample size with a total of 90 respondents consisted of 30 students, 30 TLE teachers, and 30 bakers were purposively selected from the division of Antipolo City.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Respondents by Group*

<i>Group</i>	<i>No. of Respondents</i>
Students	30
TLE Teachers	30
Bakers	30
Total	90

Instruments

To collect the data, the researcher used a survey questionnaire. The researcher sought the assistance of 10 experts to guarantee that the survey questionnaire was valid. The test was conducted on consumers with ten students and ten teachers outside the sample to check for possible misunderstandings. After that, the questionnaire was revised where appropriate by the researcher.

The nine-point hedonic rating scale with corresponding description was used in this study to determine the level of acceptability of “PEELNAPPLE” cookies in terms of Appearance, Aroma, Taste, and Texture.

Table 2. *Scale, Range, and Verbal Interpretation*

<i>Scale</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
9	8.12–9.00	Extremely Acceptable (EA)
8	7.23–8.11	Very Much Acceptable (VMA)
7	6.34–7.22	Moderately Acceptable (MA)
6	5.45–6.33	Slightly Acceptable (SA)
5	4.56–5.44	Fairly Acceptable (FA)
4	3.67–4.55	Slightly Unacceptable (SU)
3	2.78–3.66	Moderately Unacceptable (MU)
2	1.89–2.77	Very much Unacceptable (VMU)
1	1.0–1.88	Extremely Unacceptable (EU)

Table 3. *Scale, Range, and Verbal Interpretation*

<i>Scale</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
5	4.21–5.00	Very High Potential (VHP)

4	3.41–4.20	High Potential (HP)
3	2.61–3.40	Moderate Potential (MP)
2	1.81–2.60	Low Potential (LP)
1	1.00–1.80	Very Low Potential (VLP)

The five-point Likert scale with a corresponding description was used in this study to determine the level of marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” cookies in terms of production cost, supply availability, and consumer demand.

Procedure

Before administering the validated questionnaire, the researcher ensured permission through a letter requesting the conduct of the survey addressed to the school heads.

Upon receiving permission to conduct the survey, the validated survey questionnaires were administered by the researcher to the respondents. The researchers allowed tasting of the “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies, and respondents answered the provided questionnaires. After administering and collecting survey questionnaires, the researcher gathered, tabulated, and analyzed all the necessary data for the research study. All questionnaires were personally administered and retrieved by the researcher.

Ethical Considerations

The confidentiality of all information received from participants was ensured, and their identities changed to codes to remain anonymous. The study implemented measures to ensure that participants were well and safe. To ensure that the Research Protocol complies with Ethical Standards, the Ethics Committee has revised and approved it. Additionally, the research was conducted concerning cultural differences, and the data collected were used honestly and accurately in the analysis and reporting.

The produced “PEELNAPPLE” cookies went through a physicochemical analysis done by the First Analytical Services and Technical Cooperative (F.A.S.T.) Laboratories. The researcher coordinated with the office through email.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered in this study.

Production of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies out of pineapple peel, banana peel, and pulp with 125 grams, 250 grams, and 375 grams

“PEELNAPPLE” cookies could be produced out of pineapple peel, banana peel, and pulp with the following procedure; a) washed banana peel and pineapple peel, b) utilized sun drying method with a drying rack fish for drying peels for 4 days, c) utilized dehydrator to remove moisture from banana pulp for 10 hours at 70 degree celsius, d) powdered dried peels using blender, e) chopped banana pulp, f) sifted powdered peels and all-purpose flour, g) measured ingredients needed such as powdered peels, baking soda, salt, butter, all-purpose flour, powdered sugar, and chopped banana pulp using a digital weighing scale, h) creamed butter, add eggs and powdered sugar using hand mixer, i) mixed in the powdered peels, chopped banana pulp and the other ingredients, j) weighted and shaped the cookies for 10 grams each, and lastly k) baked for 15 minutes at 350 degrees Fahrenheit.

Physicochemical Analysis of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 125 Grams, 250 Grams, and 375 Grams of Pineapple Peel, Banana Peel, and Pulp

Table 4 shows the physicochemical analysis of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies, which involves examining factors such as pH level, moisture content, potassium, and salmonella (microbial analysis).

Table 4. *Physicochemical Analysis of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies*

Parameters	Unit	Test Method	Result
pH (50%) Dispersion	-----	Electrometry	5.40 @ 23.3 °C
Moisture	g/100 g	Vacuum Oven Drying	6.91
Potassium	mg/100 g	Flames AES	655
Salmonella Detection, per 25g	-----	Conventional – Presumptive	Negative

Note: The report analysis is from the First Analytical Services and Technical Cooperative (F.A.S.T.) Laboratories – Cubao

In determining whether a substance was acidic or fundamental, pH testing was carried out. It measured the hydrogen activity and its potential, as well as the level of acidity or alkalinity in foodstuffs. The pH range was 0 to 14, a value of 7 means neutral, while the level of acidity in food could be measured as low as 7, indicating that it contained an increased amount of alkaline. Moreover, the pH range was from 0 to 14.

Foods with a value between 4 and 4.5 were considered neutral or acidic. In addition, knowing the food's pH level will help to determine how to prolong the shelf life and prevent the growth of bacteria that may cause food spoilage, such as the importance of food pH, n.d. therefore, “PEELNAPPLE” cookies have 5.40 at 23.3C of potential hydrogen (pH) and are less acidic since the test result was lower than

7.0 based on the results of a physicochemical analysis conducted

The moisture content of the food has a decisive effect on its longevity. The slow growth of microorganisms in foods with low humidity makes it necessary to analyze and control food moisture. The moisture content has an impact on the taste, weight, appearance, and shelf life of food. Therefore, “PEELNAPPLE” cookies have a 6.91 moisture content implying that the lower the moisture in food, the lower the risk of food spoilage.

Potassium is an essential mineral that is required by every tissue in your body (Australia, 2023) because it carries a small electrical charge that increases the functions of different cells and nerves, it is often called an electrolyte. Many foods and supplements contain potassium in its natural form. It plays an essential role in the body, helping to maintain a regular fluid balance within our cells. In addition, potassium increases muscle contraction and supports regular blood pressure. That's why there's 655 potassium in the “PEELNAPPLE” cookies, which means there's a lot of potassium in cookies. It is important to aim for the consumption of 4,700mg of potassium per day from food by an adult in good health.

Salmonella is a bacterium that can cause diarrhea, fever, and stomachache. The bacteria may be present inside and outside of the eggs, which appear to be healthy. If there are raw or cooked eggs in them, this bacterium can lead to illness. Salmonella bacteria may be present in almost all raw foods and most people are infected with poultry or eggs that have not been cooked properly. Salmonella bacteria are killed in the food through cooking and pasteurization. There are several ways to reduce your risk of salmonella while preparing food such as washing your hands before and after preparing food or eating and cooking foods to a safe temperature before eating. Don't handle any other foods while working with raw meat, poultry, seafood, or eggs, wash or peel vegetables and fruits before cutting, eating, or cooking. On the other hand, “PEELNAPPLE” cookies had a negative result for salmonella which means it's safe to eat.

This was analyzed by the First Analytical Services and Technical Cooperative (F.A.S.T.) Laboratories – Cubao. Therefore, the nutrients detected in the analysis are present in research cookies.

Level of Acceptability of the “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies as Evaluated by Students, TLE Teachers, and Bakers with 125 Grams, 250 Grams, and 375 Grams of Pineapple Peel, Banana Peel, and Pulp

For the 125-gram Proportion

In terms of appearance, Table 5 shows the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability of Pineapple Peel, Banana Peel, and Pulp with a 125-gram proportion.

Table 5 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated the appearance with an overall weighted mean of 7.83, 7.87 interpreted as Very Much Acceptable (VMA), and 7.44 interpreted as Moderately Acceptable (MA).

This implies that both the TLE teachers and students expressed a higher level of acceptance towards the cookies' appearance than the baker respondents. This could be attributed to the bakers' extensive cookie preparation experience, making them highly skilled in recognizing the ideal appearance of cookies.

Consequently, it suggests that the product should be enhanced to make it more favorable to the market, as indicated by the lowest rating given by the bakers.

Table 5. Respondents' Evaluations on the Level of Acceptability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in 125 Grams Proportion as to Appearance

Indicators	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. It has a unique appearance.	8.03	VMA	8.00	VMA	7.50	VMA
2. It is enticing to eat	7.87	VMA	7.77	VMA	7.30	MA
3. It has a uniform shape.	7.53	VMA	7.90	VMA	7.63	VMA
4. It has well-blended cookies with pineapple banana peel and pulp.	8.00	VMA	7.80	VMA	7.57	VMA
5. It has an acceptable appearance for commercial purposes.	7.73	VMA	7.87	VMA	7.20	MA
Overall Weighted Mean	7.83	VMA	7.87	VMA	7.44	MA

In terms of Aroma, Table 6 shows the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability of Pineapple Peel, Banana Peel, and Pulp with 125 grams proportion. Table 6 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated the aroma with an overall weighted mean of 8.17, interpreted as Very Much Acceptable (VMA), 7.47, and 7.29 interpreted as Moderately Acceptable (MA).

This implies that the aroma of the cookies produced is highly favored by the student respondents. They assessed the smell of the cookies as ideal, as indicated by the highest rating in indication number 2.

Table 6. Respondents' Evaluations on the Level of Acceptability of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 125 Grams Proportion as to Aroma

Indicators	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. It has a natural smell of fruit flavor.	8.20	VMA	7.63	VMA	7.57	VM A
2. It has an ideal aroma for cookies.	8.47	VMA	7.63	VMA	7.20	MA
3. It has a delicate milky smell.	8.07	VMA	7.13	MA	7.33	MA
4. It has a desirable smell.	7.97	VMA	7.43	MA	7.13	MA
5. The smell of cookies arouses your desire to taste it.	8.17	VMA	7.53	VMA	7.20	MA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.17	VMA	7.47	MA	7.29	MA

However, TLE teachers and Baker respondents both agreed that they found the aroma of the cookies to be moderately acceptable. This suggested that the cookies should adjust some ingredients to achieve a more desirable aroma, as it received the lowest rating from the bakers who are highly skilled in preparing cookies.

In terms of taste, Table 7 shows the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability of Pineapple Peel, Banana Peel, and Pulp with a 125-gram proportion.

Table 7 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated the taste with an overall weighted mean of 8.23, 7.82 interpreted as Very Much Acceptable (VMA), and 7.39 interpreted as Moderately Acceptable (MA). This implies that both the students and teachers had a favorable opinion regarding the flavor of the produced cookies. They found the cookies enjoyable to eat and noted that there was no lingering taste of the raw materials.

Table 7. Respondents' Evaluations on the Level of Acceptability of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 125 Grams Proportion as to Taste

Indicators	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. It has a delicious taste.	8.30	VMA	7.87	VMA	7.40	MA
2. It is palatable.	7.87	VMA	7.87	VMA	7.13	MA
3. Has a well-balanced taste.	8.20	VMA	7.57	VMA	7.30	MA
4. Enjoyable to eat and has no aftertaste.	8.40	VMA	7.93	VMA	7.53	VMA
5. Has a pleasing and well-blended flavor.	8.37	VMA	7.87	VMA	7.57	VMA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.23	VMA	7.82	VMA	7.39	MA

This was reflected in the highest rating given by both groups of respondents. In contrast, the baker's response differs, suggesting that the cookies produced in 125 grams should modify some ingredients to produce a more palatable taste, as they received the lowest rating across all the indicators.

In terms of texture, Table 8 shows the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability of Pineapple Peel, Banana Peel, and Pulp with 125-grams proportion. Table 8 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated the texture with an overall weighted mean of 8.06, with 7.55 interpreted as Very Much Acceptable (VMA), and 7.41 interpreted as Moderately Acceptable (MA).

Table 8. Respondents' Evaluations on the Level of Acceptability of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 125 Grams Proportion as to Texture

Indicators	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Has an acceptable crunchy texture.	7.57	VMA	7.47	MA	7.43	MA
2. It is chewable.	7.87	VMA	7.37	MA	7.23	MA
3. It has an even texture.	8.10	VMA	7.57	VMA	7.57	VM A
4. Has a slightly soft texture.	8.27	VMA	7.47	MA	7.40	MA
5. It looks presentable.	8.50	EA	7.87	VMA	7.43	MA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.06	VMA	7.55	VMA	7.41	MA

Note: WM – Weighted Mean VI – Verbal Interpretation

This implies that the student respondents like the texture of the cookies. The high indication for the presentation of the cookies further suggests that students are more inclined to purchase them when they are available in the market. Both TLE teachers and bakers concur that the cookies produced have a consistently smooth texture. This suggests that cookies weighing 125 grams have a desirable texture like commercially available cookie products.

For the 250-gram Proportion

In terms of Appearance, Table 9 shows the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability of Pineapple Peel, Banana Peel, and Pulp with a 250-gram proportion.

Table 9 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated the appearance with an overall weighted mean of 7.89, with 7.07 interpreted as Very Much Acceptable (VMA), and 6.79 interpreted as Moderately Acceptable (MA).

Table 9. Respondents' Evaluations on the Level of Acceptability of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 250 Grams Proportion as to Appearance

Indicators	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. It has a unique appearance.	7.97	VMA	7.07	MA	6.87	MA
2. It is enticing to eat	7.83	VMA	7.10	MA	6.63	MA
3. It has a uniform shape.	7.93	VMA	7.20	MA	6.70	MA
4. It has well-blended cookies with pineapple banana peel and pulp.	7.77	VMA	6.90	MA	7.13	MA
5. It has an acceptable appearance for commercial purposes.	7.93	VMA	7.07	MA	6.63	MA
Overall Weighted Mean	7.89	VMA	7.07	MA	6.79	MA

This implies that the student respondents perceived the cookies at 250 grams as distinct and likely to be well-received in the market. This finding suggests that the students are likely to purchase the cookies once sold in the market, as the appearance of the product is one of the key elements influencing consumer buying decisions. However, the TLE teachers and bakers provided a somewhat satisfactory answer, indicating that changes need to be made to enhance the visual appeal of the cookies. This group of respondents has extensive cookie preparation experience, making them highly skilled in recognizing the ideal appearance of cookies.

Though the evaluations of the three groups of respondents vary, they were in the bracket of acceptability, which is from Moderately Acceptable (MA) to Very Much Acceptable (VMA). The pineapple peel, banana peel, and pulp, in 250 grams, were accepted when evaluated in the five indicators by the three groups of respondents regarding appearance.

In terms of Aroma, Table 10 shows the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability of Pineapple Peel, Banana Peel, and Pulp with a 250-gram proportion.

Table 10. Respondents' Evaluations on the Level of Acceptability of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 250 Grams Proportion as to Aroma

Indicators	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. It has a natural smell of fruit flavor.	8.13	VMA	7.20	MA	7.17	MA
2. It has an ideal aroma for cookies.	7.90	VMA	6.93	MA	6.87	MA
3. It has a delicate milky smell.	7.60	VMA	6.40	SA	6.73	MA
4. It has a desirable smell.	7.63	VMA	6.80	MA	7.00	MA
5. The smell of cookies arouses your desire to taste it.	7.97	VMA	6.93	MA	6.67	MA
Overall Weighted Mean	7.85	VMA	6.85	MA	6.89	MA

Table 10 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated the aroma with an overall weighted mean of 7.85, interpreted as Very Much Acceptable (VMA), 6.85, and 6.89 interpreted as Moderately Acceptable (MA).

This implies that the aroma of the cookies produced is highly favored by the student respondents. They assessed whether the smell of the cookies aroused their desire to taste it, as indicated by the highest rating in indicator number 5. However, TLE teachers and Baker respondents both agreed that they found the aroma of the cookies to be moderately acceptable. This suggests that the cookies should adjust some ingredients to achieve a more delicate milky smell as it receives the lowest rating.

In terms of taste, Table 11 shows the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability of Pineapple Peel, Banana Peel, and Pulp with a 250-gram proportion.

Table 11. Respondents' Evaluations on the Level of Acceptability of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 250 Grams Proportion as to Taste

Indicators	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. It has a delicious taste.	7.70	VMA	6.93	MA	6.80	MA
2. It is palatable.	7.77	VMA	6.83	MA	6.60	MA
3. Has a well-balanced taste.	7.67	VMA	6.77	MA	6.67	MA
4. Enjoyable to eat and has no aftertaste.	7.60	VMA	6.67	MA	6.53	MA
5. Has a pleasing and well-blended flavor.	7.60	VMA	6.80	MA	6.87	MA
Overall Weighted Mean	7.67	VMA	6.80	MA	6.69	MA

Table 11 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated the taste with an overall weighted mean of 7.67, interpreted as Very Much Acceptable (VMA), 6.80, and 6.69 interpreted as Moderately Acceptable (MA).

This implies that both teachers and bakers held a somewhat positive view of the taste of the cookies created at a proportion of 250 grams. Indicator number 4 received the lowest rating compared to all other indicators across all groups of respondents. This indicates that the recipe should be modified to make the cookies more delightful to consume. Moreover, the results indicate that the cookies have an excellent taste, as seen by the favorable evaluations received by this indicator. In terms of texture, Table 12 shows the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability of Pineapple Peel, Banana Peel, and Pulp with a 250-gram proportion.

Table 12. Respondents' Evaluations on the Level of Acceptability of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 250 Grams Proportion as to Texture

Indicators	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Has an acceptable crunchy texture.	7.50	VMA	6.60	MA	7.07	MA
2. It is chewable.	7.73	VMA	6.53	MA	6.83	MA
3. It has an even texture.	7.73	VMA	6.70	MA	6.60	MA
4. Has a slightly soft texture.	7.60	VMA	6.43	SA	6.70	MA
5. It looks presentable.	8.07	VMA	7.07	MA	6.70	MA
Overall Weighted Mean	7.73	VMA	6.67	MA	6.78	MA

Note: WM – Weighted Mean
 VMA – Very Much Acceptable
 SA – Slightly Acceptable
 VI – Verbal Interpretation
 MA – Moderately Acceptable

Table 12 showed that the Students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated the texture with an overall weighted mean of 7.73, interpreted as Very Much Acceptable (VMA), 6.67, and 6.78 interpreted as Moderately Acceptable (MA).

This implies that the student respondents prefer the texture of the cookies. The strong suggestion for the appearance of the cookies further implies that students are more likely to buy them when they are offered in the market. This finding aligns with the evaluation of TLE teachers since indication 5 received the highest grade in terms of teacher reaction. Bakers appreciate the cookies for their crispy texture.

For the 375-gram Proportion

In terms of appearance, Table 13 shows the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability of Pineapple Peel, Banana Peel, and Pulp with a 375-gram proportion in appearance.

Table 13 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated the appearance with an overall weighted mean of 7.27, 6.93, interpreted as Moderately Acceptable (MA), and 6.28, interpreted as Slightly Acceptable (SA).

This implies that the cookies with a proportion of 375 grams were perceived as somewhat pleasant by both student and teacher respondents. Both parties concurred that the cookies possess a consistent shape. Student respondents value the distinctive appearance of the cookies, indicating that young people are likely to enjoy them based on their visual appeal. However, bakers consider the cookies created to be just marginally satisfactory, with the lowest grade among the three proportions in terms of appearance. This suggests that modifications to the ingredients are necessary to attain a more appealing appearance for commercial purposes.

Table 13. Respondents' Evaluations on the Level of Acceptability of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 375 Grams Proportion as to Appearance

Indicators	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. It has a unique appearance.	7.73	MA	7.03	MA	6.33	SA
2. It is enticing to eat	7.07	MA	6.63	MA	6.07	SA
3. It has a uniform shape.	7.37	MA	7.00	MA	6.57	MA
4. It has well-blended cookies with pineapple banana peel and pulp.	7.23	MA	7.00	MA	6.40	SA
5. It has an acceptable appearance for commercial purposes.	6.97	MA	7.00	MA	6.03	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	7.27	MA	6.93	MA	6.28	SA

Note: WM – Weighted Mean; VI – Verbal Interpretation; VMA – Very Much Acceptable; MA Moderately Acceptable SA – Slightly Acceptable

Table 14 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated the aroma with an overall weighted mean of 7.07, 6.69 interpreted as Moderately Acceptable (MA), and 6.15 interpreted as Slightly Acceptable (SA).

Both students and teachers preferred the aroma of the cookies created. Both individuals preferred the cookies' natural and fruity aroma, which received the highest rating among all factors. Nevertheless, the bakers surveyed deemed the aroma to be somewhat satisfactory. Indicator 2 had the lowest rating out of all the indicators. This implies that the cookies should modify some elements to attain a more

optimal smell for the produced cookie.

Table 14. Respondents' Evaluations on the Level of Acceptability of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 375 Grams Proportion as to Aroma

Indicators	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. It has a natural smell of fruit flavor.	7.37	MA	7.07	MA	6.30	SA
2. It has an ideal aroma for cookies.	7.13	MA	6.80	MA	6.00	SA
3. It has a delicate milky smell.	6.97	MA	6.27	SA	6.03	SA
4. It has a desirable smell.	7.00	MA	6.63	MA	6.27	SA
5. The smell of cookies arouses your desire to taste it.	6.87	MA	6.70	MA	6.17	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	7.07	MA	6.69	MA	6.15	SA

Note: WM – Weighted Mean; VI – Verbal Interpretation; MA – Moderately Acceptable; SA – Slightly Acceptable

In terms of taste, Table 15 shows the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability of Pineapple Peel, Banana Peel, and Pulp with a 375-gram proportion.

Table 15 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated the taste with an overall weighted mean of 6.82, interpreted as Moderately Acceptable (MA), 6.32, and 6.20 interpreted as Slightly Acceptable (SA). This implies that cookies produced in a proportion of 375 grams received a positive response from the student respondents. They found the taste of cookies enjoyable, as it obtained the highest rating.

Table 15. Respondents' Evaluations on the Level of Acceptability of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 375 Grams Proportion as to Taste

Indicators	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. It has a delicious taste.	6.87	MA	6.67	MA	6.17	SA
2. It is palatable.	7.03	MA	6.33	SA	6.17	SA
3. Has a well-balanced taste.	6.87	MA	6.10	SA	6.30	SA
4. Enjoyable to eat and has no aftertaste.	6.37	SA	6.13	SA	6.20	SA
5. Has a pleasing and well-blended flavor.	6.97	MA	6.37	SA	6.17	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	6.82	MA	6.32	SA	6.20	SA

Note: WM – Weighted Mean; VI – Verbal Interpretation; MA – Moderately Acceptable; SA – Slightly Acceptable

Table 16. Respondents' Evaluations on the Level of Acceptability of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 375 Grams Proportion as to Texture

Indicators	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Has an acceptable crunchy texture.	7.27	MA	6.50	MA	6.23	SA
2. It is chewable.	7.13	MA	6.43	SA	6.17	SA
3. It has an even texture.	7.57	VMA	6.47	SA	6.50	MA
4. Has a slightly soft texture.	6.57	MA	6.23	SA	6.27	SA
5. It looks presentable.	7.17	MA	6.77	MA	6.23	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	7.14	MA	6.48	SA	6.28	SA

Note: WM – Weighted Mean; VI – Verbal Interpretation; MA – Moderately Acceptable; SA – Slightly Acceptable

Tables 17, 18, and 19 show the summary evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability of Pineapple Peel, Banana Peel, and Pulp with 125 grams, 250 grams, and 375 grams proportions. Table 17 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies with 125 grams as the grand weighted mean of 8.07, 7.68 interpreted as Very Much Acceptable (VMA), and 7.38 interpreted as Moderately Acceptable (MA).

Table 17. Summary of Respondents' Evaluations on the Level of Acceptability of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 125 Grams Proportion

	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
a. Appearance	7.83	VMA	7.87	VMA	7.44	MA
b. Aroma	8.17	VMA	7.47	MA	7.29	MA
c. Taste	8.23	VMA	7.82	VMA	7.39	MA
d. Texture	8.06	VMA	7.55	VMA	7.41	MA
Grand Weighted Mean	8.07	VMA	7.68	VMA	7.38	MA

Note: WM – Weighted Mean; VI – Verbal Interpretation; MA – Moderately Acceptable; SA – Slightly Acceptable

Slightly Acceptable

The results shown in Table 17 indicated that the cookies weighing 125 grams received the highest rating among all the proportions tested, making them highly preferred by both student and teacher responses. The results also indicated that the taste of the 125-gram portions was well-liked by all categories of respondents. However, the bakers had varying opinions. They considered cookies weighing 125 grams to be somewhat acceptable. Based on this, it can be inferred that certain features should be adjusted to elicit a more favorable response from this group of responders. The findings of this study aligned with the research conducted by Oguntoyinbo et al. (2022), which showed that incorporating banana peels into flour to create innovative cookie products was well-received by the participants. Furthermore, the use of banana peel flours in wheat composite has demonstrated potential in producing cookies with improved nutritional content in comparison to utilizing wheat only.

Table 18 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 250 grams as the grand weighted mean of 7.79, interpreted as Very Much Acceptable (VMA), 6.85 and 6.79 interpreted as Moderately Acceptable (MA).

Table 18. *Summary of Respondents’ Evaluations on the Level of Acceptability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in 250 Grams Proportion*

	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
a. Appearance	7.89	VMA	7.07	MA	6.79	MA
b. Aroma	7.85	VMA	6.85	MA	6.89	MA
c. Taste	7.67	VMA	6.80	MA	6.69	MA
d. Texture	7.73	VMA	6.67	MA	6.78	MA
Grand Weighted Mean	7.79	VMA	6.85	MA	6.79	MA

Note: WM – Weighted Mean; VI – Verbal Interpretation; MA – Moderately Acceptable; SA – Slightly Acceptable

The student respondents had a higher proportion of favorable ratings compared to the teachers and bakers, who considered the manufactured cookies to be moderately acceptable. This outcome suggests that modifications need to be made in all aspects to accommodate the preferences of many professional respondents.

Furthermore, the research indicated that the cookies being created are more likely to be embraced by a younger demographic, which is a positive sign that this set of consumers will support the product. These findings were consistent with the results of Bello et al. (2024), which suggested that using pineapple flour as an ingredient has the potential to create sustainable products like cookies. Both experiments yielded positive results, as participants accepted the cookie samples that were provided.

Table 19 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 375 grams as the grand weighted mean of 7.08, 6.61 interpreted as Moderately Acceptable (MA) and 6.23 interpreted as Slightly Acceptable (SA).

Table 19. *Summary of Respondents’ Evaluations on the Level of Acceptability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in 375 Grams Proportion*

	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
a. Appearance	7.27	MA	6.93	MA	6.28	SA
b. Aroma	7.07	MA	6.69	MA	6.15	SA
c. Taste	6.82	MA	6.32	SA	6.20	SA
d. Texture	7.14	MA	6.48	SA	6.28	SA
Grand Weighted Mean	7.08	MA	6.61	MA	6.23	SA

Note: WM – Weighted Mean; VI – Verbal Interpretation; MA – Moderately Acceptable; SA – Slightly Acceptable

This implies that both students and teachers evaluated the cookies produced at a proportion of 375 grams at the same level. The results suggested that both groups of respondents favored the appearance of the cookies and overall accepted them to a moderate extent. However, the results indicated that bakers consider the cookies created to be only marginally acceptable. This suggested that significant adjustments need to be made to the 375-gram proportion of the cookies to meet customer preferences. These findings aligned with the study conducted by Alam (2020), which demonstrated that the use of banana and banana peel flour in the production of food items, such as cookies, leads to an elevated level of customer preference. Moreover, the replacement of ordinary flour with banana and banana peel flour led to a significant elevation in the quantities of ash and crude fiber found in the cookies.

Significant Differences Among the Evaluations of the Three Groups of Respondents on the Level of Acceptability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 125 Grams, 250 Grams, and 375 Grams of Pineapple Peel, Banana Peel, and Pulp

Tables 20 to 27 show the Significant Differences Among the Evaluations of the Three Groups of Respondents on the Level of Acceptability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with Three Different Proportions.

In terms of appearance, Tables 20 and 21 show the evaluation of the acceptance of the three groups of respondents on the Acceptability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 125 grams, 250 grams, and 375 grams proportions.

Table 20. *Kruskal-Wallis Test of Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in Different Proportions as to Appearance*

Proportions	Statistic	Df	P-value	α	Decision	Interpretation
125g	1.749	2	0.417	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
250g	14.832	2	0.000	0.05	Reject the H_0	Significant
375g	7.533	2	0.023	0.05	Reject the H_0	Significant

Note: *Significant if $P\text{-value} \leq \alpha = 0.05$ df – Degrees of Freedom H_0 – Null Hypothesis

As seen from Table 20, the P-values (0.000, 0.023) of the 250-gram and 375-gram proportions are less than the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the statistical decision is to reject the null hypothesis. This means there are significant differences in evaluating the three groups of respondents on the acceptability level of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in 250-gram and 375-gram proportions regarding appearance.

The data shown in Table 20 indicated that there is no statistically significant difference in the ratings of the three groups of respondents when it comes to the appearance of cookies produced with a proportion of 125 grams. This suggests that all respondents agreed on the degree of acceptability of the cookies. However, there was a substantial difference in the proportions of 250 grams and 375 grams, indicating that the three groups of respondents have different opinions on the acceptability of cookies in terms of appearance.

Table 21 exhibited that the P-values (0.000, 0.014, 0.024) of the 250-gram and 375-gram proportions are below the 0.05 significance level. The statistical decision leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. So, there is a significant difference between the evaluation of the following pairs: (1) bakers and students and (2) students and TLE teacher's respondents on the level of acceptability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies concerning appearance.

In the 250-gram and 375-gram proportions, the student respondents received the highest rating; in the 375-gram proportions, the baker respondents received the lowest rating.

Table 21. *Dunn Bonferroni's Pairwise Comparisons of Respondents' Evaluations Acceptability Level of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in Different Proportions as to Appearance*

Comparison	z-Value	P-Value	Results
For 250 grams			
Bakers – Students	3.68	0.000	Means are different*
Bakers - TLE Teachers	0.85	1.000	Means are not different
Students - TLE Teachers	2.83	0.014	Means are different*
For 375 grams			
Bakers – Students	2.65	0.024	Means are different*
Bakers - TLE Teachers	1.94	0.159	Means are not different
Students - TLE Teachers	0.72	1.000	Means are not different

Note: *Significant if $P\text{-value} \leq \alpha = 0.05$ W_i, W_j - Sum of Ranks

Due to the substantial disparity in the proportions of 250 and 375 grams, a Dunn Bonferroni's Pairwise Comparison was performed to determine whether a group of respondents exhibited a significant difference.

Table 21 indicated a notable disparity in the perception of appearance between bakers and students when it comes to a weight of 250 grams. This discrepancy was also observed between students and teachers. Furthermore, there was a substantial difference between bakers and students at 375 grams proportion.

This implies that there was a particular quality of appearance that the students find appealing, but that was not preferred by bakers. It was advisable to modify the ingredients in these proportions to establish consensus among diverse groups of consumers.

In terms of aroma, Tables 22 and 23 show the evaluation of the acceptance of the three groups of respondents on the acceptance of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 125 grams, 250 grams, and 375 grams proportions.

Table 22. *Kruskal-Wallis Test of Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in Different Proportions as to Aroma*

Proportions	Statistic	Df	P-value	α	Decision	Interpretation
125g	13.141	2	0.001	0.05	Reject the H_0	Significant
250g	12.790	2	0.002	0.05	Reject the H_0	Significant
375g	6.651	2	0.036	0.05	Reject the H_0	Significant

Note: df – Degrees of Freedom H_0 – Null Hypothesis

It was evident from Table 22 that the P-values (0.001, 0.002, 0.036) of the three proportions were smaller than the 0.05 level of

significance. Hence, the null hypothesis should be rejected based on statistical analysis. This implies significant differences in evaluating the three groups of respondents on the acceptability level of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in 125 grams, 250 grams, and 375 grams proportions regarding aroma.

It demonstrated that all groups of respondents exhibit different levels of acceptance of aroma, regardless of the proportions. This finding suggested that the three groups of participants had varying criteria for evaluating the aroma of the cookies that were made. Furthermore, students had a greater preference for the aroma of the cookies produced. This is because consumers in this age range relate the appearance of their food to other aspects such as aroma.

As specified in Table 23, the P-values (0.001, 0.045, 0.006, 0.006, 0.034) of the three proportions were lower than the 0.05 significance level. Consequently, the statistical decision entails the rejection of the null hypothesis. Thus, there is a significant difference between the evaluation of the following pairs: (1) bakers and students and (2) students and TLE teacher respondents on the level of acceptability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies concerning aroma.

Table 23. *Dunn Bonferroni's Pairwise Comparisons of Respondents' Evaluations Acceptability Level of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in Different Proportions as to Aroma*

Comparison	z-Value	W _i	W _j	P-Value	Results
For 125 grams					
Bakers – Students	3.54	35.067	58.900	0.001	Means are different*
Bakers - TLE Teachers	1.11	35.067	42.533	0.801	Means are not different
Students - TLE Teachers	2.43	58.900	42.533	0.045	Means are different*
For 250 grams					
Bakers – Students	3.08	38.650	59.400	0.006	Means are different*
Bakers - TLE Teachers	0.03	38.650	38.450	1.000	Means are not different
Students - TLE Teachers	3.11	59.400	38.450	0.006	Means are different*
For 375 grams					
Bakers – Students	2.53	36.017	53.067	0.034	Means are different*
Bakers - TLE Teachers	1.69	36.017	47.417	0.272	Means are not different
Students - TLE Teachers	0.84	53.067	47.417	1.000	Means are not different

Note: *Significant if $P\text{-value} \leq \alpha = 0.05$

Table 23 indicated a notable difference in the perception of aroma between bakers and students when it comes to a weight of 125 grams. This discrepancy was also observed between students and teachers. This was also true with 250 grams and 375 grams proportions. This suggested that the students were attracted to a specific aromatic sense of the produced cookies that bakers less favored. It is recommended to adjust the ingredients in these ratios to achieve agreement among various segments of consumers.

Due to the substantial disparity in the level of acceptability in all proportions produced, a Dunn Bonferroni's Pairwise Comparison was performed to determine whether a group of respondents exhibited a significant difference.

In the three proportions, the student respondents garnered the highest ratings among all respondent groups, whereas in the 375 grams proportion, the baker respondents obtained the lowest rating.

In terms of taste, Tables 24 and 25 show the evaluation of the Acceptability of the three groups of respondents on the Acceptability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 125 grams, 250 grams, and 375 grams proportions.

As viewed in Table 24, the P-values (0.017, 0.002) of the 125- and 250- grams proportions were below the 0.05 significance level. This means that the null hypothesis should be rejected. Accordingly, there are significant differences in evaluating the three groups of respondents on the acceptability level of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in 125- and 250-gram proportions regarding taste.

Table 24. *Kruskal-Wallis Test of Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in Different Proportions as to Taste*

Proportions	Statistic	Df	P-value	α	Decision	Interpretation
125g	8.127	2	0.017	0.05	Reject the H ₀	Significant
250g	12.700	2	0.002	0.05	Reject the H ₀	Significant
375g	2.728	2	0.256	0.05	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant

Note: df – Degrees of Freedom Ho – Null Hypothesis

The results reported in Table 24 indicated that three groups of respondents have the same levels of approval at 375 grams proportions. This indicated that these ratios are advantageous for the manufacture of cookies. Furthermore, there was a noticeable disparity in the acceptability when comparing the 125- and 250- gram proportions. This suggested that the perception of these proportions varies in terms of the standard of the three categories of respondents.

Table 25 described that the P-values (0.013, 0.003, 0.016) of the 125-gram and 250-gram proportions were lesser than the 0.05 significance level. The statistical decision leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is a significant difference between the evaluation of the following pairs: (1) bakers and students and (2) students and TLE teacher respondents on the level of

acceptability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies concerning taste. In the 125g and 250g proportions, the student respondents got the highest ratings among all respondent groups, whereas in the 250 grams proportion, the baker respondents gave the lowest rating.

Table 25. *Dunn Bonferroni's Pairwise Comparisons of Respondents' Evaluations Acceptability Level of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in Different Proportions as to Taste*

Comparison	z-Value	Wi	Wj	P-Value	α	Results
For 125 grams						
Bakers – Students	2.84	35.567	54.683	0.013	0.05	Means are different*
Bakers - TLE Teachers	1.59	35.567	46.250	0.336	0.05	Means are not different
Students - TLE Teachers	1.26	54.683	46.250	0.629	0.05	Means are not different
For 250 grams						
Bakers – Students	3.31	36.900	59.200	0.003	0.05	Means are different*
Bakers - TLE Teachers	0.52	36.900	40.400	1.000	0.05	Means are not different
Students - TLE Teachers	2.79	59.200	40.400	0.016	0.05	Means are different*

Note: *Significant if P-value $\leq \alpha = 0.05$

Due to the substantial disparity in the level of acceptability in the produced cookies at 125 and 250 grams, a Dunn Bonferroni's Pairwise Comparison was performed to determine whether a group of respondents exhibited a significant difference.

Table 25 showed that there was a discrepancy in the evaluation of bakers and students for 125 grams, this is also seen for 250 grams. Moreover, students and teachers had different views on 250 grams. These results imply that the respondents have varying views of their standards of cookies in terms of taste. Students are more likely to prefer the taste of the produced cookies in all proportions making them differ significantly from another group of respondents. It was advised to modify the ingredients in these proportions to establish consensus among diverse groups of consumers.

Tables 26 and 27 show the evaluation of the Acceptability of the three groups of respondents on the Acceptability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 125 grams, 250 grams, and 375 grams proportions in terms of texture.

As shown in Table 26, the P-value (0.000) of the 250-gram proportion was lower than the 0.05 significance level. The statistical decision implies the rejection of the null hypothesis. So, there are significant differences in evaluating the three groups of respondents regarding the acceptability level of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in 250 grams in terms of texture.

Table 26. *Kruskal-Wallis Test of Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in Different Proportions as to Texture*

Proportions	Statistic	Df	P-value	α	Decision	Interpretation
125g	4.637	2	0.098	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
250g	16.060	2	0.000	0.05	Reject the H_0	Significant
375g	4.600	2	0.100	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant

Note: df – Degrees of Freedom H_0 – Null Hypothesis

The data presented in Table 26 indicated a notable disparity in the assessment of three groups of participants about the proportion of 250 grams. This result suggested that there were varying criteria used to assess the texture of the cookies that were made. The age group of respondents could have a significant impact on this comparison. Youngsters tend to determine the texture quality based on external appearance or packaging, whereas specialists such as teachers and experienced bakers have more comprehensive criteria for evaluating the cookies produced.

Table 27. *Dunn Bonferroni's Pairwise Comparisons of Respondents' Evaluations Acceptability Level of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in Different Proportions as to Texture*

Comparison	z-Value	Wi	Wj	P-Value	α	Results
For 250 grams						
Bakers – Students	3.39	38.250	61.067	0.002	0.05	Means are different*
Bakers - TLE Teachers	0.16	38.250	37.183	1.000	0.05	Means are not different
Students - TLE Teachers	3.55	61.067	37.183	0.001	0.05	Means are different*

Note: *Significant if P-value $\leq \alpha = 0.05$

Table 27 implied that the P-values (0.002, 0.001) of the 250-gram proportion are smaller than the 0.05 significance level. This means that the null hypothesis should be rejected. Thus, there is a significant difference between the evaluation of the following pairs: (1) bakers and students and (2) students and TLE teacher respondents on the level of acceptability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies concerning texture. In the 250 grams proportion, the student respondents attained the highest rating among the respondents.

Due to the substantial disparity in the level of acceptability in the produced cookies at 250 grams, a Dunn Bonferroni's Pairwise Comparison was performed to determine whether a group of respondents exhibited a significant difference.

The data shown in Table 27 indicated a notable disparity in the response between bakers and students. The response of students and teachers was the same. Furthermore, there was no substantial difference in the responses of bakers and teachers. This indicated that the

experts assessed the cookies produced at a weight of 250 grams using the same standard since they possess the same level of proficiency in evaluating food items. Student respondents prioritized the appearance of food and typically base their overall opinion on this aspect when they are satisfied.

Tables 28, 29, and 30 summarize the Kruskal-Wallis Test of Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 125 grams, 250 grams, and 375 grams Proportions.

Table 28. Summary of Kruskal-Wallis Test of Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 125 Grams Proportion

Criteria	P-Value	α	Decision	Interpretation
a. Appearance	0.417	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
b. Aroma	0.001	0.05	Reject the H_0	Significant
c. Taste	0.017	0.05	Reject the H_0	Significant
d. Texture	0.098	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant

Table 28 showed that in terms of appearance and texture at 125 grams the responses are significantly different. This implies that adjustments must be made to satisfy the standards of different groups of respondents. The findings are connected to research conducted by Da Silva et al. (2021) where they used pineapple peel flour and banana to assess the general acceptability and sensory attributes of pastry items. Both studies indicate that respondents had positive reactions to the sensory aspects.

As reflected in Table 29, the evaluations of the students, TLE teachers, and baker respondents on the acceptability level of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 250 grams proportion regarding appearance, aroma, taste, and texture denote significant differences. The P-values (0.000, 0.002, 0.002, 0.000) were less than the 0.05 significant level. This showed that the evaluations of the respondents vary significantly.

Table 29. Summary of Kruskal-Wallis Test of Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 250 Grams Proportion

Criteria	P-Value	α	Decision	Interpretation
a. Appearance	0.000	0.05	Reject the H_0	Significant
b. Aroma	0.002	0.05	Reject the H_0	Significant
c. Taste	0.002	0.05	Reject the H_0	Significant
d. Texture	0.000	0.05	Reject the H_0	Significant

Table 29 showed that in terms of appearance, aroma, taste, and texture at 250 grams the responses are significantly different. This indicates that modifications need to be made to meet the requirements of a diverse range of consumers. This outcome is associated with the research conducted by Da Silva et al. (2021), where pineapple peel flour and banana were used to assess the general acceptability and sensory attributes of pastry goods. Both studies indicate that respondents had positive reactions to the sensory characteristics.

Table 30 depicts that the evaluations of the students, TLE teachers, and baker respondents on the acceptability level of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 375 grams proportion of appearance and aroma imply significant differences. The P-values (0.023, 0.036) are smaller than the 0.05 significant level. This proves that the respondents' evaluations differ except for taste and texture.

Table 30. Summary of Kruskal-Wallis Test of Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 375 Grams Proportion

Criteria	P-Value	α	Decision	Interpretation
a. Appearance	0.023	0.05	Reject the H_0	Significant
b. Aroma	0.036	0.05	Reject the H_0	Significant
c. Taste	0.256	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
d. Texture	0.100	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant

Table 30 showed that in terms of appearance and aroma at 375 grams, the responses are significantly different. Consequently, modifications need to be made to meet the specific requirements of various respondent groups. This finding pertained to the research carried out by Khatun et al (2021) on the use of ripe banana peel flour (BPF) as a substitute for wheat flour (WF) in the production of biscuits. Both studies indicated a favorable acceptance of the pastry products that were made.

Level of Marketability of Prepared "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies with 125 Grams, 250 Grams, and 375 Grams of Pineapple Peel, Banana Peel, and Pulp in Terms of the Given Criteria as Perceived by the Three Groups of Respondents

For the 125-gram Proportion

Table 31 shows the perceptions of the three groups of respondents on the Marketability of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies with 125 grams proportion in terms of Production Cost.

Table 31 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated the production cost with an overall weighted mean of

4.52, 4.51, interpreted as Very High Potential (VHP), and 4.41, interpreted as High Potential (HP).

The data presented in Table 31 demonstrated that both the TLE teachers and students exhibited a greater degree of marketability towards the production cost of the cookies in comparison to the baker responses. This indicates that both students and professors concur that the cookies manufactured have significant potential for a successful sale in the market. Indicator 2 received the highest rating because “PEELNAPPLE” cookies can be baked in the user's kitchen.

Table 31. Respondents' Perceptions on the Level of Marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in 125 Grams Proportion as regards Production Cost

Indicators	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Ingredients cost less.	4.70	VHP	4.60	VHP	4.47	HP
2. Requires less effort to make the product.	4.20	HP	4.43	HP	4.23	HP
3. It can be prepared in your kitchen.	4.83	VHP	4.57	VHP	4.50	VHP
4. Little manpower is needed to make the product.	4.37	HP	4.50	VHP	4.47	HP
5. It needs a little capital to produce the product.	4.50	VHP	4.43	HP	4.40	HP
Overall Weighted Mean	4.52	VHP	4.51	VHP	4.41	HP

Both respondents also expressed a preference for the lower cost of cookie production. However, the baker respondents perceived the production cost as having significant potential for being high, possibly due to their existing experience in the sector of pastry production. It is advisable to heed the opinions of these specialists to enhance the product more.

The perceptions of the three groups of respondents vary from each other. Still, was within the bracket of marketability, which is from High Potential (HP) to Very High Potential (VHP). The “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 125 grams proportion were accepted when perceived in the five indicators by the three groups of respondents as to production cost.

Table 32 shows the perceptions of the three groups of respondents on the Marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 125 grams proportion in Supply Availability.

Table 32. Respondents' Perceptions on the Level of Marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in 125 Grams Proportion as regards Supply Availability

Indicators	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Bananas and pineapple fruit are available all year long.	4.47	HP	4.20	HP	4.07	HP
2. Raw materials could be easily produced.	4.37	HP	4.33	HP	4.07	HP
3. Ingredients are abundant everywhere.	4.47	HP	4.17	HP	4.17	HP
4. Ingredients are locally available.	4.67	VHP	4.57	VHP	4.40	HP
5. It needs less effort to produce.	4.30	HP	4.37	HP	4.27	HP
Overall Weighted Mean	4.45	HP	4.33	HP	4.19	HP

Table 32 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated the supply availability with an overall weighted mean of 4.45, 4.33, and 4.19 interpreted as High Potential (HP).

The data shown in Table 32 indicated unanimous agreement among respondents regarding the marketability of the cookies produced at 125 grams. They expressed a strong belief in the high potential of these cookies in the market when they are sold. Both students and teachers agreed that the ingredients for the cookie product are readily available in the market and have great potential as ingredients for producing cookies.

Nevertheless, the baker respondents viewed the supply availability as having considerable potential, likely because of their prior experience in the pastry industry. It is recommended to consider the viewpoints of these experts to suggest other raw materials that are available all year round.

Table 33 shows the perceptions of the three groups of respondents on the Marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 125 grams proportion in terms of Consumer Demand.

Table 33. Respondents' Perceptions on the Level of Marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in 125 Grams Proportion as regards Consumer Demand

Indicators	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product can meet the consumer's demand.	4.43	HP	4.20	HP	4.40	HP
2. It can satisfy consumers because of its nutritional value.	4.63	VHP	4.43	HP	4.27	HP
3. It could be sold at a lower price compared to other	4.60	VHP	4.60	VHP	4.37	HP

commercially prepared cookies.						
4. Could be consumed by people of all ages	4.70	VHP	4.53	VHP	4.37	HP
5. Meet consumer's taste and preference	4.30	HP	4.33	HP	4.37	HP
Overall Weighted Mean	4.53	VHP	4.42	HP	4.35	HP

Table 33 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated the consumer demand with an overall weighted mean of 4.53 as Very High Potential (VHP), 4.42, and 4.35 as High Potential (HP).

The data presented in Table 33 indicated that the student respondents showed a preference for the cookies that were produced in terms of consumer demand. Their ranking was indicative of significant potential. Due to its appeal to individuals of all age groups. This suggested that the cookies were generally appealing to individuals of all age groups. Furthermore, both teachers and bakers concurred that the cookies produced have significant market potential. This suggested that based on expert opinions, adjustments could be made to ensure that the cookies, weighing 125 grams, align with customer demand.

For the 250-gram Proportion

Table 34 shows the perceptions of the three groups of respondents on the Marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 250 grams proportion in terms of Production Cost.

Table 34. Respondents’ Perceptions on the Level of Marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in 250 Grams Proportion as regards Production Cost

Indicators	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Ingredients cost less.	4.47	HP	4.40	HP	4.30	HP
2. Requires less effort to make the product.	4.17	HP	4.33	HP	4.13	HP
3. It can be prepared in your kitchen.	4.57	VHP	4.40	HP	4.43	HP
4. Little manpower is needed to make the product.	4.33	HP	4.37	HP	4.37	HP
5. It needs a little capital to produce the product.	4.33	HP	4.33	HP	4.47	HP
Overall Weighted Mean	4.37	HP	4.37	HP	4.34	HP

Note: VHP - Very High Potential HP - High Potential

Table 34 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and baker’s respondents rated the production cost with an overall weighted mean of 4.37, 4.37, and 4.34 interpreted as High Potential (HP).

The data shown in Table 34 indicated a consensus agreement among all respondents on the marketability level of production cost. This result suggested that they perceived the cookies they made to have significant market potential. Indicator number 2 indicated that the product had the lowest rating among the three groups of respondents, suggesting that changes should be made in the cookie-making process to reduce the required effort. It was advised to document the standardized recipe as a reference for cookie production. However, all three groups of respondents concurred that the cookies can be made in one's kitchen. This suggests that the production of this product does not necessitate large-scale machinery and equipment.

Table 35 shows the perceptions of the three groups of respondents on the Marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 250 grams proportion in Supply Availability.

Table 35 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated the supply availability with an overall weighted mean of 4.31, 4.31, and 4.12 interpreted as High Potential (HP)

The data in Table 35 showed the agreement among three groups of respondents in terms of supply availability at 250 grams proportion. The raw ingredients for the cookie product are readily available in the market and have great potential as ingredients for producing cookies.

Table 35. Respondents’ Perceptions on the Level of Marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in 250 Grams Proportion as regards Supply Availability

Indicators	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Bananas and pineapple fruit are available all year long.	4.33	HP	4.23	HP	3.97	HP
2. Raw materials could be easily produced.	4.23	HP	4.27	HP	4.03	HP
3. Ingredients are abundant everywhere.	4.30	HP	4.13	HP	4.13	HP
4. Ingredients are locally available.	4.47	HP	4.53	VHP	4.20	HP
5. It needs less effort to produce.	4.20	HP	4.37	HP	4.27	HP
Overall Weighted Mean	4.31	HP	4.31	HP	4.12	HP

Nevertheless, the baker respondents gave the lowest rating in terms of supply availability as having considerable potential, presumably due to their previous expertise in the field of pastry. To ensure a consistent supply of alternative raw materials year-round, it was recommended to consider the viewpoints of these specialists.

Table 36 shows the perceptions of the three groups of respondents on the Marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 250 grams proportion in terms of Consumer Demand.

Table 36. Respondents’ Perceptions on the Level of Marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in 250 Grams Proportion as regards Consumer Demand

Indicators	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product can meet the consumer's demand.	4.33	HP	4.17	HP	4.23	HP
2. It can satisfy consumers because of its nutritional value.	4.27	HP	4.30	HP	4.30	HP
3. It could be sold at a lower price compared to other commercially prepared cookies.	4.53	VHP	4.50	VHP	4.20	HP
4. Could be consumed by people of all ages	4.53	VHP	4.33	HP	4.17	HP
5. Meet consumer's taste and preference	4.30	HP	4.23	HP	4.30	HP
Overall Weighted Mean	4.39	HP	4.31	HP	4.24	HP

Table 36 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated the consumer demand with an overall weighted mean of 4.39, 4.31, and 4.24 interpreted as High Potential (HP).

This implies that the “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 250 grams proportion for student respondents, indicators 3 and 4 were interpreted as Very High Potential (VHP), and indicators 1, 2, and 5 were interpreted as High Potential (HP). For the TLE Teachers respondents, indicator 3 was interpreted as Very High Potential (VHP), and the rest indicator was interpreted as High Potential (HP). All indicators were interpreted as High Potential (HP) for baker respondents.

The data shown in table 36 indicated a positive agreement from all groups of respondents. They unanimously acknowledged that the 250-gram cookies have significant business potential in terms of consumer demand. The student response asserted that the “PEELNAPPLE” cookie can be marketed at a reduced price compared to professionally manufactured cookies due to the utilization of vegetables as raw components. This belief was also shared by the responders who are teachers and bakers.

The perceptions of the three groups of respondents vary from each other. Still, was within the bracket of marketability, which was High Potential (HP). The “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 250 grams proportion were accepted when perceived in the five indicators by the three groups of respondents as to consumer demand.

For the 375-gram Proportion

Table 37 shows the perceptions of the three respondents on the Marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 375 grams proportion in terms of Production Cost.

Table 37 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated the production cost with an overall weighted mean of 4.17, 4.38, and 4.25 interpreted as High Potential (HP).

The data presented in Table 37 showed the agreement of all groups of respondents that the produced cookies in 375 grams have high potential in the market. Likewise, with other proportions indicators respondents believed that the cookies could be produced in their kitchen. This implies that the production does not require big machinery and equipment. Furthermore, it can be observed that the respondents thought that adjustments should be made to simplify and facilitate the preparation process.

Table 37. Respondents’ Perceptions on the Level of Marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in 375 Grams Proportion as regards Production Cost

Indicators	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Ingredients cost less.	4.27	HP	4.43	HP	4.30	HP
2. Requires less effort to make the product.	3.90	HP	4.33	HP	4.13	HP
3. It can be prepared in your kitchen.	4.40	HP	4.43	HP	4.30	HP
4. Little manpower is needed to make the product.	4.17	HP	4.43	HP	4.23	HP
5. It needs a little capital to produce the product.	4.13	HP	4.27	HP	4.27	HP
Overall Weighted Mean	4.17	HP	4.38	HP	4.25	HP

Note: VHP - Very High Potential HP - High Potential

The perceptions of the three groups of respondents vary from each other. Still, was within the bracket of marketability, which is High

Potential (HP). The “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 375 grams proportion were accepted when perceived in the five indicators by the three groups of respondents as to production cost.

Table 38 shows the perceptions of the three groups of respondents on the Marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 375 grams proportion in Supply Availability.

Table 38. Respondents’ Perceptions on the Level of Marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in 375 Grams Proportion as regards Supply Availability

Indicators	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Bananas and pineapple fruit are available all year long.	4.23	HP	4.20	HP	3.97	HP
2. Raw materials could be easily produced.	4.00	HP	4.27	HP	3.97	HP
3. Ingredients are abundant everywhere.	4.00	HP	4.17	HP	4.10	HP
4. Ingredients are locally available.	4.13	HP	4.57	VHP	4.30	HP
5. It needs less effort to produce.	3.90	HP	4.27	HP	4.23	HP
Overall Weighted Mean	4.05	HP	4.29	HP	4.11	HP

Table 38 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated the supply availability with an overall weighted mean of 4.05, 4.29, and 4.11 interpreted as High Potential (HP).

The data shown in Table 38 indicated a positive consensus across the three groups of respondents. Student respondents had the lowest rating among all indicators. The outcome varies across different proportions because student respondents consistently provide the highest level of response. Based on this outcome, it could be deduced that out of the proportions generated, 375 grams was the least desirable for the younger set of participants.

Table 39 shows the perceptions of the three groups of respondents on the Marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 375 grams proportion in terms of Consumer Demand.

Table 39. Respondents’ Perceptions on the Level of Marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in 375 Grams Proportion as regards Consumer Demand

Indicators	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product can meet the consumer's demand.	4.07	HP	4.13	HP	4.27	HP
2. It can satisfy consumers because of its nutritional value.	4.10	HP	4.30	HP	4.17	HP
3. It could be sold at a lower price compared to other commercially prepared cookies.	4.13	HP	4.60	VHP	4.20	HP
4. Could be consumed by people of all ages	4.13	HP	4.43	HP	4.17	HP
5. Meet consumer's taste and preference	4.23	HP	4.27	HP	4.37	HP
Overall Weighted Mean	4.13	HP	4.35	HP	4.23	HP

Table 39 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated the consumer demand with an overall weighted mean of 4.13, 4.35, and 4.23 interpreted as High Potential (HP).

The data in Table 39 presented the agreement of three groups of respondents that the produced cookies in 375 grams in terms of consumer demand have high potential in the market. Likewise in the observation of supply availability, student respondents gave the lowest rating. The outcome differed among different proportions because student respondents consistently provide the highest degree of response. From this result, it could be inferred that among the produced proportions, 375 grams is the least preferred by the younger participants.

Tables 40, 41, and 42 show the summary perceptions of the three groups of respondents on the Marketability of PEELNAPPLE Cookies with 125 grams, 250 grams, and 375 grams proportions.

Table 40. Summary of Respondents’ Perceptions on the Level of Marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in 125 Grams Proportion

	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
a. Production Cost	4.52	VHP	4.51	VHP	4.41	HP
b. Supply Availability	4.45	HP	4.33	HP	4.19	HP
c. Consumer Demand	4.53	VHP	4.42	HP	4.35	HP
Grand Weighted Mean	4.50	VHP	4.42	HP	4.32	HP

Table 40 showed that the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 125 grams as the grand weighted mean of 4.50, interpreted as Very High Potential (VHP), 4.42, and 4.32, interpreted as High Potential (HP).

Based on the data shown in Table 40, it could be deduced that student respondents have the greatest favorable response in all indicators when the proportion is 125 grams. Teachers and bakers were evaluated at an almost equivalent level. This outcome suggested that the proportion of cookies created would be more likely to be preferred by young consumers.

Furthermore, it was advised to solicit the input of educators and pastry chefs regarding how the ratio can be more advantageous within their specific age group. The findings align with the research undertaken by Soberano et al (2023), which also involved the participation of industry professionals such as bakers. The evaluation of both items received a positive response. The study's findings highlighted the potential and practicality of using banana peel flour as a replacement for regular flour in muffin creation, however, this study focused on cookie production.

Each group of respondents holds different perceptions, yet they aligned regarding production cost, supply availability, and consumer demand.

Table 41 shows the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 250 grams as the grand weighted mean of 4.36, 4.33, and 4.23, interpreted as High Potential (HP).

Table 41. *Summary of Respondents’ Perceptions on the Level of Marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in 250 Grams Proportion*

	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
a. Production Cost	4.37	HP	4.37	HP	4.34	HP
b. Supply Availability	4.31	HP	4.31	HP	4.12	HP
c. Consumer Demand	4.39	HP	4.31	HP	4.24	HP
Grand Weighted Mean	4.36	HP	4.33	HP	4.23	HP

The data shown in Table 41 demonstrated a positive consensus about the assessment of the cookies produced at a weight of 250 grams. Respondents agreed that the cookie product has significant potential for commercialization. The student gave the highest rating among the respondents, indicating that the cookie will be well-liked by the younger demographic. The ratings of teachers and bakers were likely to be similar. In their study, Salleh et al. (2020) utilized pineapple powder as a component in pastry items and assessed their marketability. This study was relevant to the present study as both investigations employed the same ingredients and received positive feedback from participants. This study signifies a notable advancement in integrating visually appealing and practical elements into cookies, providing a healthier alternative for refreshment.

Each group of respondents holds different perceptions, yet they aligned regarding production cost, supply availability, and consumer demand.

Table 42 shows the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents rated “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 375 grams as the grand weighted mean of 4.12, 4.34, and 4.20, interpreted as High Potential (HP).

Table 42. *Summary of Respondents’ Perceptions on the Level of Marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in 375 Grams Proportion*

	Respondents					
	Students		TLE Teachers		Bakers	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
a. Production Cost	4.17	HP	4.38	HP	4.25	HP
b. Supply Availability	4.05	HP	4.29	HP	4.11	HP
c. Consumer Demand	4.13	HP	4.35	HP	4.23	HP
Grand Weighted Mean	4.12	HP	4.34	HP	4.20	HP

Table 42 data indicated that all three groups of respondents contend that the marketability of the cookies produced at a weight of 375 grams was favorable. The results indicated that student respondents provided the lowest ranking in comparison to teachers and bakers. This data indicated that the proportion of 375 grams is the least preferred among young consumers. Additionally, it was recommended to seek the expertise of educators and pastry chefs on how to optimize the ratio for their respective age groups. This study was aligned with the study conducted by Sawant et al (2023), which examined different ratios of biscuits with banana peel flour. The findings revealed that a proportion of 20% was not well-received by the participants. This data could be valuable for future researchers seeking to enhance the proportion to make both products more appealing to consumers.

Significant Differences Among the Perceptions of the Three Groups of Respondents on the Level of Marketability of Prepared “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with 125 Grams, 250 Grams and 375 Grams of Pineapple Peel, Banana Peel and Pul

Table 43 shows the significant difference among the evaluations of three respondents on the level of marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with Different Proportions in terms of production cost.

Table 43. *Kruskal-Wallis Test of Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability Level of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in Different Proportions in terms of Production Cost*

Proportions	Statistic	Df	P-value	α	Decision	Interpretation
125g	0.451	2	0.798	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
250g	0.040	2	0.980	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
375g	1.730	2	0.421	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant

As summarized in Table 43, the P-values (0.798, 0.980, 0.421) of the three proportions were higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Consequently, the statistical decision is to retain the null hypothesis. This signifies that there are no significant differences in the perception of the three groups of respondents on the level of marketability of prepared “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies as regards production costs.

The data presented in Table 43 suggested that there is no statistically significant difference in the ratings of the three groups of respondents about the marketability of cookies made about production cost. All respondents unanimously agreed that “PEELNAPPLE” cookies, regardless of the proportions, have significant market potential. There was unanimous agreement that the cookies could be made at a lower cost, with less effort, and could be cooked in a local kitchen without the need for large machinery or equipment. Additionally, they concurred that less manpower was necessary, and it demanded a lower amount of capital for production.

Table 44 shows the significant difference among the evaluations of three respondents on the level of marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with Different Proportions in terms of supply availability.

As stated in Table 44, the P-values (0.164, 0.232, 0.417) of the three proportions were more than the 0.05 significance level. Hence, the null hypothesis was retained. This suggested that there were no significant differences in the perception of the three groups of respondents on the level of marketability of prepared “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies regarding supply availability.

Table 44. *Kruskal-Wallis Test of Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability Level of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in Different Proportions in terms of Supply Availability*

Proportions	Statistic	Df	P-value	α	Decision	Interpretation
125g	3.621	2	0.164	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
250g	2.925	2	0.232	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
375g	1.751	2	0.417	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant

The data presented in this table suggested that there was no statistical significant difference in the ratings of the three groups of respondents about the marketability of cookies made about supply availability. All respondents collectively concurred that “PEELNAPPLE” cookies, regardless of the ratios, possess significant market potential. All of them agree that the raw ingredients used in the production of “PEELNAPPLE” cookies are readily available throughout the year and may be quickly manufactured. Furthermore, the marketability of the cookies would be enhanced due to the abundant availability of local ingredients and the lower capital requirements.

Table 45 shows the significant difference among the evaluations of three respondents on the level of marketability of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies with Different Proportions in terms of consumer demand.

Table 45 suggested that the P-values (0.416, 0.254, 0.699) of the three proportions were more significant than the 0.05 significance level. Accordingly, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. This suggested that there are no significant differences in the perception of the three groups of respondents on the level of marketability of prepared “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies regarding consumer demand.

Table 45. *Kruskal-Wallis Test of Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability Level of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies in Different Proportions in terms of Consumer Demand*

Proportions	Statistic	Df	P-value	α	Decision	Interpretation
125g	1.752	2	0.416	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
250g	2.743	2	0.254	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
375g	0.715	2	0.699	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant

The data presented in this table suggested that there was no statistically significant difference in the ratings of the three groups of respondents about the marketability of cookies made about consumer demand. They reached a positive consensus that the “PEELNAPPLE” cookies are capable of satisfying customer demand and include a significant level of nutritious content. They also concurred that the cookies they manufacture can be offered at a lesser price compared to commercially made cookies due to the lower cost of raw ingredients. Ultimately, it was unanimously agreed that the cookies manufactured would satisfy consumers of all ages and preferences.

Tables 46,47 and 48 show the summary of the Kruskal-Wallis Test of Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability Level of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 125 grams, 250 grams and 375 grams proportion.

Table 46 shows the summary of the Kruskal-Wallis Test of Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability Level of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 125 grams proportion.

Table 46. Summary of Kruskal-Wallis Test of Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability Level of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 125 grams Proportion

Criteria	P-Value	α	Decision	Interpretation
a. Consumer Demand	0.798	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
b. Supply Availability	0.164	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
c. Production Cost	0.416	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant

It is apparent in Table 46 that the perceptions of the students, TLE teachers, and baker respondents on the marketability level of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 125 grams proportion in terms of consumer demand, supply availability, and production cost did not imply significant differences. The P-values were above the 0.05 significant level. This supported the idea that the respondents' perceptions were the same.

The data presented in this table suggested that there is no statistically significant difference in the ratings of the three groups of respondents about the marketability of cookies at 125 grams proportion. This implies that the "PEELNAPPLE" cookies have a high potential level of marketability once sold in the market, they met the criteria in terms of consumer demand, supply availability, and production cost.

Table 47 shows the summary of the Kruskal-Wallis Test of Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability Level of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 250 grams proportion.

Table 47. Summary of Kruskal-Wallis Test of Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability Level of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 250g Proportion

Criteria	P-Value	α	Decision	Interpretation
a. Consumer Demand	0.980	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
b. Supply Availability	0.232	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
c. Production Cost	0.254	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant

As supported by Table 47, the perceptions of the students, TLE teachers, and bakers respondents on the marketability level of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 250 grams proportion regarding consumer demand, supply availability, and production cost did not show significant differences. The corresponding P-values are higher than the 0.05 significant level. This affirmed that the respondents' perceptions are alike. The data presented in this table suggested that there is no statistically significant difference in the ratings of the three groups of respondents about the marketability of cookies at 250 grams proportion. This implies that the "PEELNAPPLE" cookies have a high potential level of marketability once sold in the market, they met the criteria in terms of consumer demand, supply availability, and production cost.

Table 48 shows the summary of the Kruskal-Wallis Test of Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability Level of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 375 grams proportion.

It can be seen from Table 48 that the perceptions of the students, TLE teachers, and baker respondents on the marketability level of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 375 grams proportion in terms of consumer demand, supply availability, and production cost did not signify significant differences. The respective P-values were more than the 0.05 significant level. This means that the respondents' perceptions were similar.

Table 48. Summary of Kruskal-Wallis Test of Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability Level of "PEELNAPPLE" Cookies in 375 grams Proportion

Criteria	P-Value	α	Decision	Interpretation
a. Consumer Demand	0.421	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
b. Supply Availability	0.417	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
c. Production Cost	0.699	0.05	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant

The data presented in this table suggested that there was no statistically significant difference in the ratings of the three groups of respondents about the marketability of cookies at 375 grams proportion. This implies that the "PEELNAPPLE" cookies have a high potential level of marketability once sold in the market, they met the criteria in terms of consumer demand, supply availability, and production cost.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were arrived at: The "PELNAPPLE" cookies with 125 grams proportion is the most acceptable proportion in terms of appearance, aroma, taste, texture, and color compared to other proportions.

In terms of physicochemical analysis the “PEELNAPPLE” cookies have a 5.40 at 23.3C of potential hydrogen (pH) and are less acidic since the test result was lower than 7.0, 6.91 moisture content implying that the lower the moisture in food, the lower the risk of food spoilage, 655 potassium which means there's a lot of potassium and negative result for salmonella which means it's safe to eat based on the results of a physicochemical analysis conducted.

From the conclusions expressed in the study, the following are at this moment recommended: (1) It needs improvement in packaging and labeling. (2) Prepared “PEELNAPPLE” cookies can be used as a market study for the school. (3) Future researchers may study the shelf life of “PEELNAPPLE” Cookies.

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